

Mechanical Failure Detection of Mica-Splitting-Copper Composite Materials Using Mechanical Measurements together with Electrical Measurements

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a technique to detect mechanical failure produced in mica-splitting-copper composite materials by means of the combined use of mechanical and electrical measurements. A series of tests such as tensile, bending, and repeated bending tests were carried out on four kinds of stator windings, which were composed of steel solid bar or copper strands and mica-splitting tapes, and were impregnated with epoxy and polyester resins. The strain, deflection, and stiffness of the stator windings were measured. At the same time, the $\tan\delta$ and breakdown voltage characteristics were also measured. Comparing the mechanical and electrical measurement results, the mechanical damage induced in the stator windings is revealed. The combined use of mechanical and electrical measurements is successful to detect microcracks in the insulation systems which are so small that their existence cannot be detected by variations in the strain and deflection.

INTRODUCTION

The trend toward turbine and water wheel generators or induction motors of bigger and bigger rating continually presents designers with new and ever more intractable problems. Among them, are the mechanical strength of stator windings subjected to various kinds of loads such as thermal expansion caused by temperature variation and mechanical vibration caused by electromagnetic forces. The stator windings are a composite structure, consisting of conductor and insulation systems. An understanding of the failure mechanism of the stator windings, therefore, is desirable not only to provide adequate design methods for existing materials, but also to enable the definition of desirable characteristics of composites for future developments. However, the studies in this area have been with only limited success (1)^v(7).

The purpose of the present study is to relate directly a measurement technique for detecting the mechanical failure produced in stator windings. In this study, four kinds of stator windings with mica-splitting tapes which were impregnated with epoxy and polyester resins were examined. The strain, deflection, and stiffness of stator windings were measured. At the same time, the $\tan\delta$ characteristic was measured, and then the mechanical damage produced in the stator windings is examined. The breakdown voltage was also measured in the last stage

of each test, and the fracture induced in the insulation is discussed. Examining the variations in stress distribution, stiffness, $\tan\delta$ characteristic, and breakdown voltage, it is clarified that the combined use of mechanical and electrical techniques provides more information about the mechanical failure produced in stator windings.

TEST SPECIMENS AND TEST PROCEDURE

Test Specimens

Fig. 1 shows cross sectional view and Table 1 gives the specifications for the test specimens. Table 2 gives the cross sectional area, moment of inertia of cross section, and modulus of elasticity of the conductor and insulation systems for the test specimens.

The test specimens were stator windings impregnated with epoxy and polyester resins, and that with two different kinds of conductors; solid mild steel and copper strands. Mica-splitting tape was wrapped around the conductor to 4.2 mm thickness and impregnated with epoxy and polyester resins. Fig. 1 (a) shows a cross section of specimens Nos. 1 and 2 having a solid mild steel bar. Fig. 1 (b) shows a cross section of specimens Nos. 3 and 4 having about 40 copper strands as well as that for actual machines. The length of the test specimens is 1140 mm.

Fig. 1 Cross sectional views of test specimens

Table 1. Specifications for test specimens

Specimen No.	Conductor		Impregnated resin
	Material	Construction	
1	Mild steel	Solid bar	Epoxy resin
2			Polyester resin
3	Copper	Strand	Epoxy resin
4			Polyester resin

Table 2. Dimensions and material constants of test specimens

Specimen No.	Conductor			Insulation		
	Cross sectional area	Moment of inertia of cross section	Modulus of elasticity in tension	Cross sectional area	Moment of inertia of cross section	Modulus of elasticity in tension
	($\times 10^2 \text{ mm}^2$)	($\times 10^3 \text{ mm}^4$)	($\times 10^4 \text{ N/mm}^2$)	($\times 10^2 \text{ mm}^2$)	($\times 10^3 \text{ mm}^4$)	($\times 10^4 \text{ N/mm}^2$)
1	6.0	7.20	2.1	6.01	3.53	7.02
2				4.75	4.76	
3	4.75	5.84	1.06	7.26	3.67	7.02
4				4.76	4.76	

Test Procedure

Tensile Test. Fig. 2 shows a view of the tensile test arrangement. As can be seen in Fig. 2, the insulation systems within a range of 120 mm from both ends were stripped off from the test specimen in order to make it easy to clamp both ends of the conductor and to apply the axial load to the test specimen. Consequently, the length of the portion covered with the insulation systems was 900 mm. In this test, both ends of the test specimens were cramped by a tensile testing machine and the axial load was applied to the test specimen. The strains produced on the insulation surface were measured by strain gauges bonded on the insulation surface of the test specimen along its length as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 A view of tensile test arrangement

The electrical characteristics such as $\tan\delta$ and breakdown voltage were also

measured to detect the mechanical failure produced in the test specimen. In this test, the axial load was applied to the test specimen up to producing the bonding failure between the conductor and the insulation systems. The tangent delta characteristics were measured at the center portion with an electrode of 600 mm length by using a Schering bridge. These measurements were performed in 50 kN steps of the axial load for specimens Nos. 1 and 2 and 10 kN steps for specimens Nos. 3 and 4. Breakdown voltage was measured after visible slips were observed at both ends of the test specimen.

Bending Test. Fig. 3 shows a schematic diagram of the bending test. As can be seen in Fig. 3, a four point loading method was used in this test. This loading method has an excellent advantage in that a uniform bending moment can form at the center portion of the test specimen. This uniform stress distribution would make it easy to analyze the test results. Thus, the strain on the insulation surface, the deflection, and $\tan\delta$ characteristics were measured at the center portion and the failure induced in the test specimen was examined from both the mechanical and electrical point of views.

Fig. 3 Schematic diagram of bending test

Strain was measured by strain gauges bonded on both insulation surfaces of the test specimen at the center portion. These gauges were connected in series in a bridge circuit so as to detect each failure caused on both insulation surfaces of the test specimen and to gain increased sensitivity. Since the output of the strain gauges was recorded with twice the actual strain produced on the insulation surface, the induced strain was obtained by dividing the recorded strain by 2.

The deflection of the test specimens was measured at five points shown with alphabetical characters from A to E in Fig. 3 and then the deflection curve was calculated by the least square method, thus eliminating the effects of local deformation at the bottom support points.

In this test, the $\tan\delta$ characteristics were also measured at the center portion with an electrode of 300 mm length. These measurements were performed under both loaded and unloaded conditions in order to detect mechanical failure electrically. Moreover, breakdown voltage was measured at the final stage.

Repeated Bending Test. The schematic diagram of the repeated bending test equipment is shown in Fig. 4. Four point loading was also used in this test. Strain gauges were mounted on the upper and bottom surfaces of the test specimen in the center portion as shown in Fig. 4. Lead wires from the strain gauges were connected to each adjacent side of a bridge in order to detect each failure caused on both surfaces of the test specimen. The bending load was measured by a dynamometer, and relative displacement between bottom support and frame was measured by a dial gauge. The flexural stiffness was calculated from the relationship between the bending load and the deflection.

Fig. 4 Schematic diagram of repeated bending test

The $\tan\delta$ characteristics were measured in the same manner as described above at each stage after a certain number of cyclic bending loads was applied. These tests were carried out at various strain amplitudes. The breakdown voltage was

measured at the last stage for each test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Relationship between Tensile Load and Strain on Insulation Surface

Fig. 5 shows the relationship between the axial load and the strain of the insulation surface when the axial load is applied to both ends of the conductor of the stator windings. It is clear from Fig. 5 that the maximum strain of the insulation surface is about 1200×10^{-6} within this test condition. The measured maximum strain is less than the ultimate tensile strain of $(1700 \text{ to } 2000) \times 10^{-6}$ for specimens Nos. 1 and 3 and $(1200 \text{ to } 1500) \times 10^{-6}$ for specimens Nos. 2 and 4. These results mean that within the load level in this test, any failure due to the tensile strain does not occur in the insulation systems, and that bonding failure between the conductor and insulation systems is induced by the reduction in the cross sectional area of the conductor at both ends because of yielding of conductor materials.

Bending Moment - Deflection and Bending Moment - Strain Relations

Figs. 6 and 7 show the bending moment - deflection and bending moment - strain relations. As can be seen in Figs. 6 and 7, the variations in the deflection and strain of the test specimens with solid mild steel bars are divided into three regions. In the primary region, the deflection and strain increase in proportion to the bending moment, when the bending load is reduced to zero, the strain and deflection also become zero. This region corresponds to a bending moment below 600 N.m for specimen No. 1 and 450 N.m for specimen No. 2. In the

Fig. 5 Relationship between axial load and strain on insulation surface

Fig. 6 Relationship between bending moment and deflection at center

Fig. 7 Relationship between bending moment and strain of insulation surface

secondary region, a nonlinear characteristic is observed between the bending moment vs. the strain and deflection relationships, followed by a tertiary region of increasingly large strain and deflection leading to failure. The nonlinear phenomenon in the secondary region is caused by the mechanical failure of insulation systems gradually expanding from the insulation surface. In the tertiary region beyond the bending moment shown in Figs. 6 and 7, a distinct color change to white was observed on the insulation surface, followed by cracking leading to failure.

Relationship between Strain Amplitude and Number of Cycles to Failure

Figs. 8 and 9 show the relationships between stiffness ratio and number of cycles for specimen Nos. 3 and 4, respectively. The ordinate of these figures shows the ratio of the stiffness EI after a number of loading cycles, to the initial stiffness (EI)₀.

Fig. 8 Relationship between stiffness ratio and number of cycles for specimen No. 3

Fig. 9 Relationship between stiffness ratio and number of cycles for specimen No. 4

As can be seen in these figures, the variation in the flexural stiffness is divided into two types with respect to strain amplitude. One of them is found in a strain amplitude beyond 650×10^{-6} for specimen No. 3 and 550×10^{-6} for specimen No. 4. In this range of the strain amplitude, there is a primary region with small change in the flexural stiffness in comparatively small number of loading cycles, followed by a secondary region of little or no stiffness reduction. The secondary region is followed by a tertiary region of increasingly large stiffness reduction leading to failure. The other of them is found in a strain amplitude below 600×10^{-6} for specimen No. 3 and 500×10^{-6} for specimen No. 4. In this range of the strain amplitude, there is a primary region with small stiffness reduction, followed by a secondary region of little or no stiffness reduction within 10^7 cycles.

Variations in Electrical Characteristics under Axial Load

Figs. 10 and 11 show the relationships between the $\tan\delta_0$ and $\Delta\tan\delta$ characteristics and the axial load applied to both conductor ends of the test specimen. The white and black marks shown in Figs. 10 and 11 denote the values of the $\tan\delta_0$ and $\Delta\tan\delta$ characteristics under loading and unloading conditions, respectively. In this paper, $\tan\delta_0$ is defined as the $\tan\delta$ value at 0.5 kV/mm and $\Delta\tan\delta$ is defined as the difference between $\tan\delta$ values at 5.0 kV/mm and 0.5 kV/mm.

As can be seen in Figs. 10 and 11, no appreciable variation is found in the $\tan\delta_0$ and $\Delta\tan\delta$ characteristics in the region below an axial load of 200 kN for specimens Nos. 1 and 2 and 60 kN for specimens Nos. 3 and 4 where the strain on the insulation surface of the test specimen increases in proportion to the axial load. In addition, no distinct difference is found in both the $\tan\delta_0$ and $\Delta\tan\delta$ characteristics under loading and unloading conditions. These results mean that any mechanical failure does not occur in the insulation systems in the region below a load of 200 kN and 60 kN. In the region beyond these load levels, where the bonding failure is forcibly produced between the copper strands and the insulation systems, appreciable variation appears in both the $\tan\delta_0$ and $\Delta\tan\delta$

Fig. 10 Relationship between $\tan \delta_0$ and axial load

Fig. 11 Relationship between $\Delta \tan \delta$ and axial load

characteristics.

In order to examine the failure mechanism of the stator windings in more detail, $\tan \delta$ characteristics were measured before and after applying an axial load of 240 kN to specimen No. 1 in which the bonding failure might be expected between the copper strands and insulation systems. The breakdown voltage characteristics were also measured at this moment. Fig. 12 shows the comparison between the $\tan \delta$ characteristics before and after loadings. It is clear that the $\tan \delta$ value becomes maximum at about 4 kV/mm in the voltage per unit thickness. This result may suggest that a comparatively uniform stratified void is produced inside the test specimen (8). This phenomenon corresponds to the bonding failure between the copper strands and the insulation systems described in the preceded section. No distinct reduction, however, is found in the breakdown voltage characteristics.

Fig. 12 $\tan \delta$ characteristics before and after tensile test

Variations in Electrical Characteristics under Bending Load

Figs. 13 and 14 show the relationship between $\tan \delta$ and $\Delta \tan \delta$ characteristics and the bending moment applied to the test specimens.

Let us now attack the problem of the failure mechanism of specimens Nos. 1 and 3, impregnated with epoxy resin. Comparing the test results for specimens Nos. 1 and 3, no appreciable variation is found in $\tan \delta_0$ and $\Delta \tan \delta$ characteristics in the primary region where the strain produced on the insulation surface and the deflection of the test specimen increase in proportion to the bending moment. In the secondary region, appreciable change appears in both the $\tan \delta_0$ and $\Delta \tan \delta$ characteristics. Comparing these results with Figs. 6 and 7, it is clear that the variation in $\tan \delta$ characteristics is caused by the failure of the insulation surface on the tensile side. When a higher bending moment is applied to the test specimen, cracks appear on the insulation surface, followed by a considerable reduction in the breakdown voltage.

Fig. 13 Relationship between $\tan \delta_0$ and bending moment

Fig. 14 Relationship between $\Delta \tan \delta$ and bending moment

Next, let us examine the failure mechanism of specimens Nos. 2 and 4 impregnated with polyester resin. Comparing the test results for specimens Nos. 2 and 4, distinct variations in the $\tan \delta$ characteristics of specimens Nos. 2 and 4 are found in the primary region. This variation has a tendency to increase in proportion to the bending moment. When the bending moment is reduced to zero, appreciable offsets are also observed in comparison with the initial values in the $\tan \delta$ characteristics. These offsets tend to increase in proportion to the bending moment. This result means that there are a lot of microcracks in the insulation systems which were so small that their existence cannot be detected by variations in the strain and deflection of specimens Nos. 2 and 4 under loading conditions. In the secondary region, the variation rates in the $\tan \delta$ characteristics are large in comparison with the rate of increase in the bending moment. This phenomenon means that the microcracks are accompanied by the failure of the insulation systems on the tension side gradually expanding from the insulation surface to the conductor. In the tertiary region, a change of color to white is observed on the insulation surface, accompanied by remarkable variations in the $\tan \delta$ characteristics, leading to drastic failure of the insulation systems in the last stage.

Accordingly, it is very interesting to examine the cause of the variations in the $\tan \delta$ characteristics even in the primary region of specimens Nos. 2 and 4. As can be seen in Figs. 10 and 11, there is no appreciable change in the $\tan \delta$ characteristics within a strain of 1200×10^{-6} on the insulation surface under axial loading. On the contrary, when a bending load is applied to specimens Nos. 2 and 4, remarkable variation is found in the $\tan \delta$ characteristics even in a comparatively small strain range on the insulation surface as shown in Figs. 13 and 14. These results suggest that the variations in the $\tan \delta$ characteristics of specimens Nos. 2 and 4 in the primary region are produced by failure induced in the insulation systems on the compression side.

Variations in Electrical Characteristics under Cyclic Bending Loading

Figs. 15 and 16 show typical examples of the variations in $\tan \delta$ characteristics under a strain amplitude of 650×10^{-6} for specimen No. 1 and 550×10^{-6} for specimen No. 2, respectively. The $\tan \delta$ characteristics of specimen No. 1 vary with a small change of about 2% in both the primary and secondary regions below 10^5 cycles. On the contrary, in the tertiary region beyond 5×10^5 cycles, the $\tan \delta$ characteristics begin to change obviously, and these follow a tremendous reduction in the breakdown voltage. This failure is caused by the failure of mica-splitting tapes, gradually expanding from the insulation surface.

In Fig. 16, a remarkable variation is found in the $\tan \delta$ characteristics of specimen No. 2 under cyclic bending loading. The variation in the $\tan \delta$

Fig. 15 Variation in $\tan \delta$ characteristics of specimen No. 1 under strain amplitude of 650×10^{-6}

Fig. 16 Variation in $\tan \delta$ characteristics of specimen No. 2 under strain amplitude of 550×10^{-6}

characteristic is caused by the bonding failure in the layer between mica-splitting tapes even under a comparatively small level of static bending loading described above. The large variation in the $\tan \delta$ characteristics of specimen No. 2, therefore, seems to be caused by the bonding failure gradually expanding in the layers between mica-splitting tapes within the primary and secondary region. In the tertiary region, however, both the $\tan \delta$ characteristics of specimens Nos. 1 and 2 are getting to be quantitatively almost the same. This seems to mean that the bonding failure in the layers between the mica-splitting tapes is accompanied by the failure of mica-splitting tapes, gradually expanding from the insulation surface in the tertiary region.

Fig. 17 shows the comparison between the $\tan \delta$ characteristics of specimen No. 1 before and after tests under a strain amplitude of 600×10^{-6} , in which little stiffness reduction is found up to 10^7 cycles. Fig. 18 shows the same

Fig. 17 Comparison between $\tan \delta$ characteristics of specimen No. 1 before and after tests

Fig. 18 Comparison between $\tan \delta$ characteristics of specimen No. 2 before and after tests

result for specimen No. 2 tested under a strain amplitude of 500×10^{-6} . Although, as can be seen in Figs. 8 and 9, little reduction in the flexural stiffness is found up to 10^7 cycles, a slight shift from the initial value is found in the $\tan\delta$ characteristics as shown in Figs. 17 and 18. This means that small damage is induced in the insulation systems by applying cyclic bending loading to the test specimens.

Fig. 19 shows the relationship between the breakdown voltage ratio and strain amplitude after tests. Below a strain amplitude of 600×10^{-6} for specimen No. 1 and 500×10^{-6} for specimen No. 2, no significant reduction in the breakdown voltage is observed. This means that there is no mechanical damage in the insulation systems leading to reduction in the breakdown voltage within these strain amplitudes. On the contrary, beyond those strain amplitudes, a remarkable reduction in the breakdown voltage is found, where the flexural stiffness is reduced to 60 to 75% of the initial value. This means that the stiffness reduction shown in Figs. 8 and 9 is caused by gradually expanded failure of the insulation systems leading to reduction in the breakdown voltage.

Fig. 19 Relationship between breakdown voltage ratio and strain amplitude after tests

CONCLUSIONS

A series of tests were carried out on four kinds of stator windings by measuring the strain, the deflection, the $\tan\delta$ characteristics, and breakdown voltage characteristics. These measurements were performed under axial, bending, and cyclic bending loadings. Some discussion were made on the failure mechanism of stator windings under existing external forces. A measurement technique, in which electrical measurements get together with mechanical measurements, was developed for the mechanical failure detection of stator windings. The results obtained are as follows:

- (1) Stator windings impregnated with epoxy resin do not break until the tensile strain produced on the insulation surface reaches the ultimate tensile strain of the insulation systems. This failure gradually expands from the insulation surface to the conductor with an increase of the bending load.
- (2) Stator windings impregnated with polyester resin are slightly broken down on the compression side even with a comparatively small strain level, the damage gradually expanding with an increase of the bending load. When the strain on the tension side reaches the ultimate tensile strain, that failure accompanies the failure on the insulation surface on the tension side, gradually expanding to the conductor leading to drastic failure.
- (3) When a strain amplitude beyond 650×10^{-6} and 550×10^{-6} is applied to the stator windings impregnated with epoxy and polyester resins, respectively, there is a primary region with small stiffness reduction of about 3 to 9% of the initial stiffness followed by a secondary region of little or no stiffness reduction. The secondary region is followed by a tertiary region of increasingly large stiffness reduction to failure.
- (4) When a strain amplitude below these values is applied to the stator windings up to 10^7 cycles, there are only the primary and secondary regions in the stiffness vs. number of cycles correlation.
- (5) The test method, using mechanical measurements such as strain and deflection together with electrical measurements such as $\tan\delta$ and breakdown voltage characteristics, is effective for examining the failure mechanism of stator windings.
- (6) The close relationship is found between the occurrence of mechanical damages and variations in the electrical characteristics. That is, the apparent

variation is found in the $\tan\delta$ characteristics when the bonding failure takes place in adhesive layer, and the remarkable reductions are observed in the breakdown voltage characteristics when the insulation systems are broken.

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Prediction of Fracture Toughness of Unidirectional Metal Matrix Composites

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ABSTRACT

The fracture toughness of unidirectional metal matrix composites is predicted in this paper. The analytical method used in the calculation is the modified Kendall's model for the crack penetrating through the fiber and takes account of the plastic work along the interface. In the present analysis, the effect of coating zone and volume fraction of fiber on the macroscopic fracture toughness is also investigated.

INTRODUCTION

In metal matrix composites, coating agents are often applied on the fibers to enhance the bonding at the matrix-fiber interface. The coating material is, in general, brittle and may contain flaws on its surface. Circumferential cracks may be initiated at the flaws and penetrate into the fiber and matrix. As the applied stress increases, this internal crack may propagate in a concentric manner and finally cause the macroscopic failure of the composites. During this process, various kinds of elastic and plastic energies which contribute to the fracture toughness of the composite are dissipated to create new crack surfaces. In the case of the metal matrix composites, the effects of the coating zone and the plastic deformation of the matrix on the fracture toughness should be taken into consideration. There have been a number of analytical models by which the mechanism of the failure of a fiber with or without a coating zone can be explained (1-4). However, no attempt has been made to compute the macroscopic fracture toughness of the metal matrix composites. In this paper, the fracture toughness of the composite is defined as the sum of the elastic strain energy release rate of the crack propagating in the composite and the plastic work done by the fiber which is pulled out of the matrix due to the crack extension.

The actual path of crack propagation may follow a zig-zag plane. The fracture toughness of the crack propagating in a zig-zag manner is larger than that for the straight crack. Hence, the fracture toughness predicted for the straight crack can be the lower bound for that of the actual composite.

In this paper, the fracture toughness of unidirectional metal matrix composites will be computed on Boron fiber-reinforced aluminum. The present analytical method is based on Kendall's model (5,6).